

First report of *Monalonia bondari* (Hemiptera: Miridae) as the causal agent of lateral shoot dieback in *Eucalyptus* spp. in Brazil and its control strategies

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Short running title: Shoot Dieback in *Eucalyptus* caused by *Monalonia bondari*

Abstract

Lateral shoot dieback has emerged as a significant disorder affecting *Eucalyptus* spp. plantations in Brazil, with increasing incidence and unclear etiology. During field observations, plant bug species (Miridae) were consistently found in symptomatic areas, raising the hypothesis of their involvement in the onset of the disease. This study aimed to identify the insect species associated with dieback symptoms, evaluate their ability to induce damage under controlled conditions, and test the efficacy of insecticides for population control. Morphological and molecular analyses confirmed the presence of *Monalonion bondari*, a mirid species previously reported as a pest in cocoa (*Theobroma cacao*), now observed infesting young Eucalyptus trees. Experimental infestations with *M. bondari* induced the characteristic shoot dieback symptoms, similar to those observed in the field, confirming its role as the causal agent. Furthermore, field trials demonstrated that applications of thiamethoxam and bifenthrin significantly reduced the insect population, with protective effects for up to 15 days post-application. These findings represent the first report of *M. bondari* damaging eucalypt in Brazil and provide evidence-based strategies for its chemical control. Implementing targeted monitoring and pest management can mitigate damage and enhance plantation sustainability.

Figure 1: Symptoms of lateral shoot dieback in eucalyptus plantations where eggs and adult plant bugs (Miridae) were found near the lesions: A- Affected trees; B- Detail of lateral shoot dieback of a single tree; C – Minicankers and secondary shoot emergence (arrow) at the insect feeding site; D- Dark lesions at the point of insect attack; E – Generalized dieback in a severely affected tree. F- Lesions on the main leaf vein; G – Detail of the adult insect and eggs (arrow) on the plant tissue.

Figure 2: Distribution of *Eucalyptus* plantations exhibiting lateral shoot dieback in southern Bahia State, where adult plant bugs specimens were observed.

Figure 3: Reproduction of symptoms caused by *Monalonion bondari* on a hybrid clone of *Eucalyptus grandis* × *E. urophylla* under controlled conditions. A – Cage containing healthy plants exposed to insect attack. B – Insect feeding on a rooted eucalypt cutting by inserting its stylets. C – Evolution of disease symptoms at 1, 3, and 5 days, respectively, after the introduction of the insects into the cage. D - Lesions along petiole and main leaf vein after 7 days.

Figure 4: Number of *Monalonion bondari* insects found in eucalypt plants in each treatment over 1 (A), 7 (B) and 15 (C) days after spraying the insecticides. In (A), (B) and (C) the bars bearing the same letters indicate similar values at the 5% significance level (Tukey post-hoc test). The lines within the boxplots represent the median, the lower and upper boundaries of the boxes represent, respectively, the 25th and 75th percentiles, while the whiskers extend to the smallest and largest values within 1.5 box lengths. The dots represent the outliers.

The sequence data generated in this study are available in GenBank and can be found below:

>OR961527.1 *Monalonion bondari* isolate MI_01 cytochrome c oxidase subunit I (COX1) gene, partial cds; mitochondrial

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>OR961528.1 *Monalonion bondari* isolate MI_02 cytochrome c oxidase subunit I (COX1) gene, partial cds; mitochondrial

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>OR961529.1 Monalonion bondari isolate MI_03 cytochrome c oxidase subunit I (COX1) gene,
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>OR961530.1 Monalonion bondari isolate MI_04 cytochrome c oxidase subunit I (COX1) gene,
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>OR961531.1 Monalonion bondari isolate MI_05 cytochrome c oxidase subunit I (COX1) gene,
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